

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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EVALUATE A CHANGE IN PRACTICE FOR PREDIABETES IN A RURAL
AMBULATORY CARE SETTING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Prediabetes is the precursor to diabetes mellitus. It is an important health condition that is largely undiagnosed or simply overlooked. Prediabetes affects more than 84 million adults in America and is growing at 4.5% annually. Without lifestyle modifications such as physical activity and diet, individuals with prediabetes are at high risk to develop diabetes mellitus type II with consequent complications. The prediabetes health crisis is significant for several reasons: large numbers of people diagnosed annually, large numbers of people undiagnosed, rapid growth rate, and rate of progression from prediabetes to diabetes. The American Diabetes Association reported in 2015 that prediabetes impacts 1 out of 3 adults in the United States.

The method used for this project was the implementation of a prediabetes algorithm in a rural ambulatory care setting in southern California. The four algorithm steps were: (1) identify and screen at-risk individuals; (2) obtain a hemoglobin A1c (HgbA1c) laboratory value for each at-risk individual; (3) confirm prediabetes diagnosis and, for those who tested positive, provide consultation on illness, need for lifestyle modifications (e.g., increase physical activity and healthy eating), enrollment into prediabetes/nutrition class; and (4) remain in contact with identified individuals and recheck HgbA1c laboratory values at 3-month intervals until the HgbA1c was below 5.6%. A paired samples *t* test was used to compare HgbA1c laboratory values between baseline and 3-month values.

Out of 264 patients, 162 returned at the 3-month interval to have their HgbA1c laboratory test repeated. Of these, 83% were Hispanic and 79% were female. Individuals completing initial and 3-month HgbA1c laboratory testing demonstrated a mean decrease of -0.314, from 5.964 to 5.650 ($p < .0001$). This would mean a decreased progression into diabetes mellitus type II. Additionally, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test indicated there was a statistically significant decrease in HgbA1c laboratory value at the 3-month follow-up in those who engaged in physical activity ($p = .013$). This would mean a decreased progression into diabetes mellitus type II. In contrast to physical activity, which did provide statistical significance in lowering HgbA1c laboratory values, prediabetes class attendance did not yield statistically significant results. However, only 37 participants attended the prediabetes class.

Preliminary data showed a positive impact on the predominately Hispanic and female prediabetic patients' HgbA1c laboratory value at the 3-month follow-up for those who were identified and received counseling on prediabetes. Further investigation is needed to identify behavior patterns, including changes to diet, types and amount of exercise, as well as changes in weight following initial counseling to determine the greatest impact on HgbA1c laboratory value reduction.

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BACKGROUND

Prediabetes is an important health condition that is largely undiagnosed or simply overlooked. It affects millions of adults in America and is growing at more than 4.5% annually (American Diabetes Association [ADA], 2015). Without lifestyle modifications, such as diet and physical activity, individuals with prediabetes are at high risk to develop diabetes mellitus type II with consequent complications such as heart disease, stroke, kidney disease, retinopathy, and neuropathies. Under normal circumstances, the body's pancreas produces a hormone called insulin, which assists to control the body's blood glucose. When someone has prediabetes, the body is not able to make enough insulin or the body is not responding to insulin properly. People with prediabetes have blood glucose levels that are elevated above the normal range but below the threshold criteria for a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus type II. The most common laboratory tests for prediabetes include Hemoglobin A1c (HgbA1c), fasting glucose (FG), and 2-hour oral glucose tolerance test (2Hr OGTT). A person is diagnosed with prediabetes when the HgbA1c laboratory value is between 5.7% and 6.4%. Prediabetes can also be diagnosed when the FG measurement is between 100 and 125 mg/dl or when 2Hr OGTT values are between 140 and 199 mg/dl (Bansal, 2015).

Significance

The prediabetes health crisis is significant for five primary reasons: large number of people diagnosed annually, large number of people undiagnosed, rapid growth rate for prediabetes, annual cost of treatment, and rate of progression from prediabetes to diabetes. The ADA reported in 2015 that 84.1 million Americans age 18 and older had prediabetes (33% of U.S. adults).

In the *National Diabetes Statistics Report*, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC; 2017) estimates 9 out of 10 people with prediabetes are not even aware they have it. In fact, 15% to 30% of people with prediabetes will develop diabetes mellitus type II within 5 years. Additionally, while the 2014 report did not provide estimates for the cost of prediabetes, the total annual cost for diagnosed diabetic patients was estimated to be \$245 billion (see Table 1). The International Diabetes Federation projects 471 million prediabetics globally by 2035 (Bansal, 2015).

Table 1

Estimated Growth in Prediabetes and Annual Cost of Treatment

Metric	Value
Estimated total number of adult diabetics in USA (18 years or older)	29.1 million
Annual cost of treating adult diabetics	\$245 billion
Estimated per person annual cost (\$245 billion/29.1 million)	\$8,419
Estimated number of adult prediabetics in USA	86 million
Estimate 20% of current prediabetics will become diabetic within the next 5 years (84.1 million x 20%)	16.8 million
Estimated total number of adult diabetics in USA next 5 years (29.1 million today + 16.8 million over next 5 years)	45.9 million
Annual cost of treating adult diabetics by 2022 (\$8,419 per person x 45.9 million people)	\$386.4 billion

Pathophysiology of Prediabetes

Prediabetes is considered to be a metabolic disorder whereby there is a defect in glucose metabolism. The food we consume is comprised of three basic nutrients: proteins, carbohydrates, and fats. As food travels to the stomach and digestion occurs, the body turns food into glucose. Under normal operation, glucose travels through the bloodstream into muscle and fat cells. The cells then use the glucose as fuel to provide

energy to the body. However, glucose cannot enter the cells without a special hormone called insulin. Insulin is produced in the pancreas by the islets of Langerhans. Insulin helps keep blood glucose levels at a normal range. When an individual has prediabetes, the body is (1) not able to make enough insulin after a meal is consumed, or (2) the body is not responding to the insulin being produced. This latter condition is known as insulin resistance.

People with prediabetes have elevated blood glucose levels above the normal range but below the threshold for diabetes mellitus type II. If prediabetes continues to progress, the individual will develop diabetes mellitus type II. Over time diabetes mellitus type II can create damage to vital organs, including eyes, kidneys, nerves, and heart. Eventually diabetes mellitus can lead to serious complications such as blindness, kidney failure, limb amputation, heart attack, and/or stroke. For patients with prediabetes, effective strategies to regulate blood glucose levels include lifestyle modifications, physical activity, and education.

In a study done by Bergman (2013), the author examined the pathophysiology of prediabetes. The author described the following deficiencies with an impaired glucose state (i.e., prediabetes) and hyperglycemia (i.e., diabetes mellitus type II): (1) insulin resistance (a decrease response to insulin by target tissues), (2) a decrease in insulin secretion by the beta cells of the pancreas, and (3) alteration in β -cell function. In a separate study by Faerch, Borch-Johnsen, Holst, and Vaag (2009), the authors discussed the pathophysiology of isolated impaired fasting glycemia and identified the following defects: (1) reduced hepatic insulin resistance, (2) stationary beta cell dysfunction and/or chronic low beta cell mass, (3) altered glucagon-like peptide-1

secretion, and (4) inappropriately elevated glucagon secretion. These authors concluded that individuals who develop combined isolated impaired fasting glycemia and isolated impaired glucose tolerance display abnormalities in both peripheral and hepatic insulin sensitivity as well as progressive loss of beta cell function. Both of these studies reveal that prediabetes is a continuum of impaired glucose regulation.

Prediabetes is not a benign condition. Research data clearly indicate increased risks of glycemic progression and microvascular and macrovascular complications (see Figure 1). This adds weight to the importance of intervention at an early stage. More so, the evidence clearly indicates that the progression to type II diabetes mellitus can be delayed or prevented through lifestyle and pharmacological interventions (Pour & Dagogo-Jack, 2011).

Project Purpose

Reports and observations in a rural ambulatory care setting in Southern California revealed inconsistent practices among providers in the areas of diagnosis, follow-up, and treatment of prediabetic patients. This rural ambulatory care setting includes 12 family physicians, three internists, one family nurse practitioner, and one diabetic educator. While laboratory tests ordered by the health care providers can be used to diagnose prediabetes, the screening of at risk individuals and the ordering of laboratory tests for prediabetes is not performed consistently. Additionally, each health care provider has a different approach to follow-up care for prediabetic patients.

Figure 1. Prediabetes progression.

Furthermore, for those diagnosed with prediabetes, the rural ambulatory care setting does not currently offer any standard education, treatment plan, or medication regimen. Given this lack of coordination and practice inconsistencies, there was an opportunity to improve outcomes for prediabetic patients. The purpose of this scholarly project was to evaluate a change in practice for the treatment of prediabetes in a rural ambulatory care setting by implementing a prediabetes algorithm.

The specific aims or objectives of the project were the following: (1) create prediabetes awareness among all primary health care providers, (2) identify at risk individuals, (3) screen at risk individuals and counsel/educate those found to be prediabetic about appropriate lifestyle modifications, (4) enroll patients with a diagnosis of prediabetes into a diabetes and nutrition class conducted by a registered dietician, (5) evaluate HgbA1c laboratory tests at 3-month intervals until HgbA1c laboratory value is 5.6% or below, and (6) decrease the progression of prediabetes into diabetes mellitus type II. The design and implementation of this change in practice would provide a more consistent approach across all primary health care providers.

This project included education/counseling on prediabetes as well as on the importance physical activity and diet to overall health. A critical component of this new approach was to repeat the HgbA1c laboratory test of at-risk patients every three months until the HgbA1c laboratory value was 5.6% or less. Early identification and treatment of prediabetic patients improves patient outcomes and saves the health care organization direct and associated costs. In summary, the clinical question was can the HgbA1c laboratory value among prediabetic patients be improved by providing counseling/education on prediabetes/diabetes to identified patients, enrolling at risk patients in a

prediabetes/ nutrition class, and advising the patient to engage in lifestyle modifications, such as physical activity and diet?

Supporting Framework

The work of developing, implementing a prediabetes algorithm and evaluating this change in practice was supported and guided by the Integration and Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Sciences (i-PARIHS) framework (see Figure 2). The i-PARIHS model is applicable to evidence-based practice and implementation projects (Kitson & Harvey, 2016). There are four core constructs to the i-PARIHS framework: (1) facilitation, (2) innovation, (3) recipients, and (4) context. The context construct can be further broken down into (1) inner context: local level, (2) inner context: organizational level, and (3) the outer context. Permission to use the framework for this project was obtained and granted (see Appendix A).

Unique to this framework is the concept of facilitation. Facilitation is the mechanism by which new information and knowledge enters clinical practice. As outlined in the model, three facilitation roles are identified in evidence-based projects: (1) novice, (2) experienced, and (3) expert facilitators. The innovation construct refers to the proposed practice change. In this project, the implementation of a prediabetes algorithm and its evaluation are the innovation. The recipient construct is viewed as the stakeholders or those individuals who are affected and influenced by the implementation (the innovation). Recipients can be individuals or groups of people.

The context construct has three different layers to take into consideration. The first layer is the characteristics of the local setting (e.g., primary care setting, such as a clinic or a hospital unit). The second layer is the inner context at the organizational level

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at
What the Facilitator Does

Characteristics of the Innovation

- Underlying knowledge sources
- Clarity
- Degree of fit (compatibility or contestability)
- Degree of novelty
- Likely boundaries
- Trialability
- Relative advantage

- Problem identification
- Acquiring/appraising evidence
- Baseline context & boundary assessment
- Stakeholder mapping

Recipients

- Motivation
- Values & beliefs
- Clinical consensus
- Local opinion leaders
- Existing data sources
- Skills and knowledge
- Time and resources
- Learning environment
- Collaboration and teamwork
- Power & authority
- Professional boundaries & networks

- Goal setting
- Consensus building
- Audit & feedback
- Improvement methods
- Project management
- Change management
- Team building
- Conflict management & resolution
- Barriers/boundary assessment
- Boundary spanning

Inner Context: Organization

- Organizational priorities
- Structure
- Leadership & senior management support
- Systems & processes
- Culture
- History of innovation & change
- Absorptive capacity

- Stakeholder engagement
- Communication & feedback
- Marketing & presentation
- Networking
- Boundary spanning
- Negotiating & influencing
- Policies & procedures

Outer Context

- Policy drivers & priorities
- Incentives & mandates
- Regulatory frameworks
- Environmental (in)stability
- Inter-organizational networks & relationships

- Political awareness & influence
- Communication
- Marketing
- Networking
- Boundary spanning
- Sustainability & spread

Inner Context: Local Level

- Formal & informal leadership support
- Culture
- Past experience of change
- Mechanisms for embedding change
- Evaluation & feedback processes

- Local context assessment
- Communication & feedback
- Networking
- Boundary assessment & spanning
- Negotiating & influencing
- Policies & procedures
- Structuring learning

Source: Harvey G & Kitson A (2015) Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in Healthcare: A facilitation guide. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge

Figure 2. The i-PARIHS framework. From *Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in Healthcare: A Facilitation Guide*, G. Harvey & A. Kitson, 2015, Abingdon, Oxon, United Kingdom: Routledge, p. 50. (Reprinted with permission).

(e.g., if the local setting is a clinic, then the hospital under which the clinic falls under would be the organizational unit).

The outer context references the health care system within which the organization is based (e.g., state and national policies and regulations) along with other issues external to the inner context such as laws/regulations and insurance norms.

i-PARIHS Framework and the Scholarly Project

The application of the i-PARIHS framework to the scholarly project revealed the following details. Four facilitators were identified at the rural ambulatory care setting, including one novice (family nurse practitioner), two experienced (family physicians), and one expert (family physician, who is the diabetes champion). The innovation was to evaluate a change in practice, using the prediabetes algorithm for the identification and treatment of prediabetes in a rural ambulatory care setting.

The recipients or the stakeholders in this setting included patients, physicians, clinical staff (registered nurses, licensed vocational nurses, medical assistants, and diabetes educators), management, information technology staff (in terms of electronic charting), and shareholders. The local context was the rural ambulatory care setting. The inner context at the organizational level was the parent hospital, which is located approximately 30-miles from the clinic. The outer context, which is comprised of the external health system, would include the hospital affiliation and the wider healthcare system. Other outer context variables considered included health care policy and health insurance plans.

The starting point in applying the framework to this project was the discussion of the innovation with key facilitators at the local rural ambulatory care setting. At each step

of implementation, barriers to getting the prediabetes algorithm implemented were evaluated; for example, barriers identified for primary health care providers and staff. Once agreement was reached on the initial version of the innovation, the project was discussed with local context recipients (excluding patients); barriers to adherence were identified and considered in order to maximize the potential success of the innovation.

Once the changes for the prediabetes algorithm were finalized (see Table 2), the prediabetes algorithm was implemented. Training of providers and staff was considered in the plan. Separate in-service meetings will need to be conducted with physicians and management as well as clinical staff. The purpose of these meetings would be to communicate the health care need to screen at-risk individuals for prediabetes, treat them at this early stage and prevent this at-risk group from going into diabetes mellitus type II, gather feedback, discuss the proposed change (innovation), and reach agreement on a date and strategies to implement such changes.

The change in practice began by identifying at risk individuals from those scheduled to be seen by the same day provider (author/facilitator of project). For those identified at risk or with risk factors, a request to have a HgbA1c laboratory test was made. The patient was instructed to visit the in-house laboratory where they could complete the blood draw. Laboratory results were available within 1-3 business days. The laboratory results confirmed or ruled-out a diagnosis of prediabetes. Patients who tested positive for prediabetes, based on HgbA1c laboratory measurements of 5.7% to 6.4%, were contacted by the author (phone call, email, voicemail, or postal mail). During the next patient communication, the laboratory results were discussed, the patient was

Table 2

Target Population: Patients at Risk for Prediabetes

Risk Factor	Comments
Age	18 or older
Family history	First degree relative (e.g., mother or father)
Body mass index (BMI)	BMI 25 to 29.9: overweight BMI \geq 30 or greater: obese
Ethnicity	American Indian, Latino (Hispanic), African American, Asian/Pacific Islanders, White
Childbirth in last 36-months	Newborn weight \geq 9 pounds or greater, and/or diagnosis of gestational diabetes during pregnancy
Elevated blood pressure	Blood pressure > 140/90 mmHg or on medication for Hypertension
Women with Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS)	PCOS characteristics: acanthosis nigricans, central adiposity, obesity, menstrual irregularities, excess facial hair growth

counseled/educated on prediabetes/diabetes, enrolled in prediabetes/nutrition class and advised to engage in lifestyle modifications, such as physical activity and diet.

A personal reminder was made on the author's schedule to follow up with the patient in 3 months. At that time, the author contacted the patient again by phone and the patient was asked to return to the clinic laboratory to get their 3-month follow-up HgbA1c laboratory test.

Once the author received the second HgbA1c laboratory value, the patient was contacted again by the author and the patient's HgbA1c laboratory test result was discussed with the patient. At this follow-up contact, the patient was asked if they had attended the prediabetes/nutrition class and if they had engaged in lifestyle modifications (physical activity and/or dietary changes).

It was anticipated that multiple iterations of the innovation were needed before arriving at a final version (see Table 3). As indicated in Figure 3, the change in practice included the collection of data, specifically designed to reveal results of the innovation on patients. The author, in conjunction with the primary facilitators, shared the data in meetings with other facilitators and made needed changes to improve the overall effectiveness of the innovation.

Table 3

Prediabetes Treatment: Context Issues and Considerations

Item	Detail
Insurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rural ambulatory clinic has multiple insurance plans - Per visit co-pay for individual patients is \$10 to \$30 - Any additional costs are not anticipated to present financial burden
Additional Labs/Tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential increase of 500 + blood draws required across target population - Assuming rate of 30 blood draws per day at rate of 5 draws/hour - Assuming no additional staff hired for this project - Anticipate taking 60- 90 days to complete all blood tests
Additional Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Registered dietitians, diabetes educators and laboratory personnel
Meeting Rooms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meeting rooms where prediabetic patients can meet with health educator - Room is reserved for this use: Classes are available throughout day and evening - Group setting environment
# of Classes Per Week	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase number of classes during the week to accommodate patient schedules (evening and weekend hours)
Printed Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide handouts and guide booklets in patients' native languages
Phone Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Registered dietitians, diabetes educators readily available via phone, email or in person to provide, support and counseling as needed
Modify Medical Record	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenge to obtain approval for needed IT spending to modify software application - Instead, will implement physical index card solution to remind health care provider - For each patient diagnosed as prediabetic follow prediabetes algorithm

Figure 3. Change in practice innovation feedback loop. From *The Lean Startup*, E. Ries, 2011, New York, NY: Crown Business, p. 75.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As part of the research for this scholarly project on prediabetes, a review of literature (ROL) was performed. The purpose of this comprehensive literature search was to build upon the findings of published, peer-reviewed research studies. To complete the ROL, electronic databases from PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar were utilized. Search filters were applied against the database repositories, so that only the most relevant studies were selected.

The following search terms and key topics were included as part of this ROL: “prediabetes,” “prediabetes and treatment interventions,” “prediabetes strategies,” “prediabetes and metformin,” “prediabetes preventions programs in rural ambulatory care clinics,” “prediabetes changing behaviors of physicians and prediabetes patient perceptions.” Additional filters included peer-reviewed studies, published in English between 2012 and 2017. Studies from across the world were considered, as were studies from ambulatory and rural care settings. The final search criteria specified that all studies include adults, 18 years of age and older. Studies excluded from the ROL search were those involving children and studies conducted in a hospital environment.

The search was focused on the following topic areas: (1) prediabetes interventions, (2) diabetes prevention programs, (3) health care provider barriers in the treatment of prediabetes, and (4) patient barriers for not seeking prediabetes treatment.

Prediabetes Treatment Interventions

A total of 10 research studies were selected for this section (see Appendix B). This included two systematic reviews, five randomized controlled trial studies, one longitudinal study, one retrospective cohort study, and one prospective randomized

parallel group design. Combined, the selected studies (excluding the systematic review) covered 20,955 patients. In a systematic review by Sun, You, Almeida, Eastabrooks, and Davy (2017), the researchers looked at 69 studies. Of this total, 32 studies were conducted in the United States and 37 were conducted in other countries. Analysis of the 10 selected studies determined that lifestyle interventions are effective in reducing body weight and glucose related outcomes (see Table 4).

Table 4

Prediabetes Treatment Interventions Literature Search: PubMed and CINAHL

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Prediabetes AND Treatment	Peer Reviewed, English Language Publish date: 2012-2017	2,626	2,000	626	10
Prediabetes AND Strategies	Peer Reviewed, English Language Publish date: 2012-2017	261	100	50	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title/abstract and relevance to project topic.

There was consistency across each of the 10 studies included. Specifically, each study identified and measured similar variables which included changes in body weight, HgbA1c laboratory values, fasting blood glucose, blood pressure, and lipid panel results. Additional considerations included the cost effectiveness of lifestyle interventions, utilization of dieticians in conducting health and nutrition classes, and the use of metformin medication in prediabetes. Lifestyle modifications addressed in the study interventions include healthy eating, portion control, balanced meals, and weight loss.

The most common dose of physical activity in the studies was 150 minutes per week, with a suggestion of five separate 30-minute light-to-moderate workouts at a

minimum. Nutrition education could be done by a registered dietician or by another health care provider.

Additional strategies tested were regular contacts by a health care provider, community health worker or health coach. In some cases, interventions delivered using technology were tested studies. Also, the use of metformin (a primary diabetes medication) was evaluated in some studies.

The aggregated evidence on this section was overwhelmingly in favor of promoting lifestyle modifications leading to better patient outcomes. Sun et al., (2017), in their meta-analysis, found that overall effect sizes for studies testing lifestyle interventions were negative for weight, 2-Hr BG, and HgbA1c laboratory values (clinically important outcomes); they also found that dietician-delivered interventions had the largest and statistically significant average effect size on weight reduction. Dunkley et al., (2014), in a meta-analysis of 25 studies testing lifestyle intervention programs that followed international guidelines, found a mean weight loss of 2.12 kg (95% CI) over 12 months. McCurley, Gutierrez, and Gallo (2017), in a meta-analysis of 12 studies testing lifestyle interventions specifically in Hispanic samples, found that weight loss and glucose regulation effect sizes were small to moderate; more importantly, they delineated the intervention elements that were associated with the highest effect sizes: literacy modification, Hispanic foods/recipes, cultural diabetes beliefs, family/friend participation, structured community input, innovative experiential learning.

Specifically, as seen in Appendix B, individual studies testing programs that included multiple components (lifestyle modifications) were found to enhance weight reduction (Sun et al., 2017), changes in eating habits (Sun et al., 2017), better HgbA1c

laboratory values (Sun et al., 2017). Moin et al., (2015) examined the use of metformin at the prediabetes stage and found lower HgbA1c laboratory values.

From these systematic reviews and study findings it is clear that helping patients achieve lifestyle modifications of physical activity and diet are vital to the success of any program designed to address prediabetes.

While this may be commonly known, without proper motivation and incentives, many people will not begin or remain in a lifestyle modification program. Thus, the key challenge is to design a program which people find interesting and are eager to participate (see Appendix B).

Findings from the Diabetes Prevention Program (United States)

Eight research studies that include data from the Diabetes Prevention Program (DPP) were included for this section of the ROL (see Table 5). The DPP was one of the largest clinical trials ever conducted. Its aim was to prevent the development of diabetes mellitus. The DPP was funded by the National Institute of Health through the National Institute of Diabetes, Digestive and Kidney Disease, Office of Research on Minority Health and the National Institute on Aging. This review included five randomized controlled trial studies and three systematic reviews. Excluding the systematic reviews, a total of 3,759 patients were studied (see Appendix C).

The DPP whose initial findings were published in February 2012 found success by bundling intensive diet and exercise advice with continuous monitoring and frequent support from trained professionals. The systematic review by McCurley et al., (2017), looked at 12 DPP studies, including six single group pre-post uncontrolled trials, five randomized controlled trials, and one quasi experimental community experimental group.

Table 5

Diabetes Prevention Program Literature Search: PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Retrieved	Articles Used
Diabetes Prevention Program	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007-2017	5,024	4,000	100	8

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

The systematic review by Mudaliar et al., (2016), looked at 44 community-based studies, all of which were based in the United States.

Each of the eight studies included in this section and featured in Appendix C (Aziz, Absetz, Oldroyd, Pronk, & Oldenburg, 2015; Herman et al., 2012; Katula et al., 2013; Ma et al., 2013; McCurley et al., 2017; Miller, Weinhold, & Haikady, 2016; Mudaliar et al., 2016; Nathan et al., 2015), provided consistent findings using the same intervention. Namely, the DPP approach which includes the above bundle and regular follow-up, resulted in increased weight loss, lowered HgbA1c laboratory values, and improved fasting blood glucose readings.

The support professionals in a DPP included community health workers, health coaches, lifestyle coaches, individual case managers, and program coordinators. For patients, inclusion in a DPP program means full support, encouragement, and incentives to success. The success of the DPP program answers the challenges stated in the section of this scholarly paper titled “prediabetes treatment interventions.” Specifically, while patients might be cognizant of the importance of diet and exercise to good health, many people lack the discipline and guidance to get started or remain engaged. The DPP program provides the missing component, in much the same way that Weight Watchers™

or Jenny Craig™ provide needed support to people who want to lose weight. A structured, formal program in a group setting that encourages participation and interaction is more successful than just good advice and a pat on the back. Clearly, the success of a prediabetes program must include DPP-like support components (see Appendix C).

Health Care Provider (HCP) Barriers in the Treatment of Prediabetes

Five research studies were included (see Appendix D). One quantitative study, one systematic review, one cross-sectional study, one randomized controlled trial and one proof of concept, pilot randomized control trial (see Table 6). Combined, the studies covered 700 primary care practices and 1,268 primary care providers.

Table 6

Physician Attitudes, Behaviors & Perceptions (Healthcare Provider Barriers to Prediabetes Treatment): Literature Search: PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Physician AND Attitudes AND Prediabetes	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2012-2017	15	10	2	2
Physician AND Behaviors AND Prediabetes	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2012-2017	3	2	1	1
Physician AND Perceptions AND Prediabetes	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2012-2017	8	5	3	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title/abstract and relevance to project topic.

Common barriers identified across these primary care practices and providers include (1) limited time to provide education and counseling to prediabetic patients, (2) HCP perception that patients do not have the motivation or interest to learn about prediabetes, (3) HCP belief that patients will not modify their lifestyle habits, (4) perceived notion that patients do not have the economic resources needed for lifestyle modification, and (5) limited resources of the health care organization to provide services that prediabetics need (Mainous, Tanner, Scuderi, Porter, & Carek, 2016).

Goldberg (2012), in a survey of primary care practices, also found that patients themselves could be barriers to care provision along with the influence of other stakeholders such as those involved in corporate matters. A tool found to improve screening/counseling and other appropriate care strategies with prediabetics served as a cue to HCPs whose patients filled out online surveys on an iPad prior to a health care visit (Lin & Mann, 2012; Mann & Lin, 2012).

Conclusions indicate that many HCP do not view prediabetes as a valid health concern (Mainous et al., 2016). As a result, patients identified as prediabetic do not get the attention they deserve. This HCP attitude is reflected in the rapid increase in the numbers of people diagnosed with prediabetes and the alarming number of people suspected to have undiagnosed prediabetes. Findings support that prediabetes education for HCP is as important as it is for the general public. It has been said that the first step in solving a problem is the recognition that a problem exists (see Appendix D).

Patient Barriers for Not Seeking Prediabetes Treatment

Five research studies were reviewed for this section (see Table 7). This included two qualitative studies, one systematic review, one cross sectional and one randomized

Table 7

Patient Attitudes, Behaviors & Perceptions (Patient Barriers to Treatment): Prediabetes Literature Search: PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Patient AND Attitudes AND Prediabetes	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2012-2017	42	38	4	1
Patient AND Behaviors AND Prediabetes	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2012-2017	303	297	4	2
Patient AND Perceptions AND Prediabetes	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2012-2017	19	17	2	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

controlled trial pilot study. Not including the systematic review, 711 patients were studied.

In the systematic review, Murray, Craigs, Hill, Honey, and House (2012) examined 32 studies. Of these, nine studies were conducted in Australia, seven from the United Kingdom, five in the United States, four each from Canada and Europe, and three from the Middle East.

Across the reviewed evidence (Kolb, Kitos, Ramachandran, Lin, & Mann, 2015; Moreno et al., 2014; Murray et al., 2012; Strauss, Rosedale, & Kaur, 2015), the most common barriers for patients not addressing prediabetes included: (1) knowledge deficit about the illness and its management, (2) misconstrued ideas about diabetes and prediabetes, (3) depression, (4) anxiety, (5) lack of support from family and friends, (6)

transportation and related costs, (7) inadequate or lack of health insurance, and (8) beliefs about causes of illness and lifestyle change.

Despite the barriers, O'Brien et al. (2016), found that patients will consider lifestyle interventions and be open to medication, if prescribed by a HCP. One of the most important conclusions that can be drawn from this section of the ROL is that the general public lacks information and knowledge of prediabetes and the high-risks of developing diabetes mellitus type II (see Appendix E).

Review of Literature Summary

Prediabetes is preventable and treatable. But progress towards reversing the rapid increase in numbers will not happen until HCPs and the general public become more informed and aware of the risks. Detection of prediabetes is fundamental to addressing the problem. The evidence confirms the overall effectiveness of well implemented DPPs, which lead to the needed lifestyle modifications of physical activity and diet. In fact, one could argue the hands-on, intensive support that a DPP program provides is the primary reason for its success.

Research indicates that up to 30% of people with prediabetes will develop diabetes mellitus type II within 5 years and up to 70% within their lifetime. Early detection, combined with lifestyle modifications hands-on DPP type support and treatment is critical to reversing this trend. Action must be taken now to prevent a health crisis that would envelop more than 50% of the population and create an explosion in health care costs that has the potential to crash the economy and devastate the health care system.

While some may consider this an overly dramatic statement, consider that the ADA (2015) estimated the annual cost of treating diabetes and prediabetes at \$322 billion. If health care costs increase at a rate of 5% annually, this health condition becomes a \$1 trillion problem within 25 years.

METHODS

The purpose of this scholarly project was to evaluate a change in practice for treating prediabetes in a rural ambulatory care setting (clinic). The primary goal for this project was to decrease the progression of type II diabetes in patients with prediabetes. The process that was followed to meet this goal, included the followings steps: (1) create prediabetes awareness among all the primary care providers at the clinic, (2) identify at-risk individuals among the author's case load, (3) screen at-risk individuals for prediabetes (HgbA1c laboratory values 5.7% to 6.4%) and counsel these patients that they are prediabetic and need to consider/engage in lifestyle modifications, (4) enroll prediabetic individuals into a prediabetes and nutrition class conducted by a registered dietician, and (5) evaluate HgbA1c laboratory tests at 3-month intervals until the HgbA1c laboratory value is under 5.6% (see Appendix F).

Setting

The setting for this scholarly project was a rural ambulatory care clinic in Southern California, in the county of Ventura. The clinic is staffed with 15 physicians (12 family medicine doctors, three internists) one family nurse practitioner (author/facilitator), one nurse educator, and one registered dietician. The primary patient population seen in this setting is Hispanic (Latino).

Sample

The clinic serves a population of approximately 25,000 patients annually, 75% of whom are estimated to be adults, 18 years of age and older. The identification and screening criteria for the project are adults with the following risk factors: (1) ethnicity (American Indian, Hispanic (Latino), African American, Asian/Pacific Islanders, and

Caucasian (White), (2) first degree family relative with diabetes mellitus type II, (3) BMI \geq 30, (4) hypertension, defined as blood pressure greater \geq 140/90 mm Hg, (5) cardiovascular disease (e.g., any of the following: atherosclerosis of the aorta, myocardial infarction, coronary artery disease, coronary artery bypass graft, and dyslipidemia), (6) age 40 + years, (7) central/visceral adiposity: measured via waist circumference or visual inspection, (8) polycystic ovarian syndrome, and (9) history of gestational diabetes. Individuals excluded from this project were those less than 18 years of age and anyone with a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus type I or II.

Ethical Considerations

The privacy of patient data during the term of this project was of utmost importance. In accordance with the Federal Drug Administration (FDA) regulations and the Institution Review Board (IRB) guidelines, a request was made and approval obtained from the health care organization for which the author was employed at the time of the project. An additional request was made and approval obtained from California State University, Fullerton (CSUF; see Appendix G and Appendix H, respectively). Thereafter, the prediabetes algorithm was implemented and data collection commenced.

Evaluating the Change in Practice

Within this setting, there was no consistent approach to the treatment of prediabetes among primary health care providers. As a result, it was believed that there was a large population of undiagnosed patients with prediabetes. This was outlined in a 2016 study performed at the University of California at Los Angeles (UCLA), reporting that most California cities have prediabetes rates in excess of 40% (Babey, Wolstein, Diamant, & Goldstein, 2016). Without intervention, up to 30% of those with prediabetes

today, will develop diabetes mellitus type II within 5 years and 70% will develop diabetes mellitus type II within their lifetime (Babey et al., 2016).

The primary care physicians at the clinic meet regularly to discuss general topics related to patient care and clinic operations. The author of this project is invited to attend these meetings. For this scholarly paper, the author asked permission to discuss this project.

A meeting was allocated to discuss this concern. The focus of the meeting was to share and disseminate current research findings detailing the scope of the prediabetes problem, as well as an “open floor” question/answer session among the family physicians (health care providers). Regular meetings with primary care providers can provide opportunities to discuss innovative strategies such as the prediabetes algorithm (see Appendix F) and work collaboratively towards addressing prediabetes. For the project to be successful, it was important that the primary care providers felt engaged and involved.

The novice facilitator (author) worked in conjunction with the expert facilitator and the prediabetes algorithm was approved. The prediabetes algorithm (change in practice) was implemented from June 2017 through December 2017. The individual activities and steps included in the innovation are outlined in Table 8.

Project Evaluation

Using the 2016 UCLA study as a baseline, the assumption was made an estimated 40% of the adult population was prediabetic at this rural ambulatory care setting. The change in practice began with the number of patients the author saw during same day appointments. A number of calculations were made to project the number of patients that

were included during the data collection period. These assumptions and calculations are outlined (see Table 9).

Table 8

Activities for Innovation Project

Activity Person	Activity or Task
Author NP (novice facilitator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Met with primary care providers at rural ambulatory care setting - Discussed prediabetes and ideas to address problem - Obtain buy-in and preliminary approval to proceed to next step - Activities will take place in the conference room of the clinic
Author NP (novice facilitator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Met with expert facilitator (diabetes champion) who is the lead family physician - Finalize details of prediabetes algorithm, implementation occurred - Objective: easy and fast to carry out, low-cost and non-disruptive - Activity will take place in the office of the expert facilitator
Nursing Staff (recipient)	<p>Additional tasks for medical assistant (MA), licensed vocational nurse (LVN) or registered nurse (RN) to perform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As patient is being processed, identify “at risk” patients for prediabetes, following steps identified in the prediabetes algorithm provided in each family medicine module - If yes, place “physical/visual marker” in the exam room on the keyboard of each computer in each of the provider exam rooms (2 exam rooms per provider) - Activity will take place in each module where the MAs, LVNs or RNs perform their duties
Health Care Provider (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate patient for chief complaint, screen for prediabetes if risk factors are present - Recognize “physical/visual marker” and order laboratory test (HgbA1c), based on previously agreed prediabetes algorithm - Activity will take place in the rural ambulatory clinic
Phlebotomist (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Draw serum blood samples of HgbA1c - Activity will take place in the laboratory setting (second floor) at the clinic
Lab Techs (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perform blood analysis on a stat or a routine basis - Update patient chart with laboratory values as soon as final HgbA1c result is obtained - Results are automatically forwarded to the provider who ordered the laboratory test - Activity will take place in the laboratory setting (second floor)
Health Care Provider (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review blood laboratory results within 3 days - Evaluate for prediabetes condition (HgbA1c laboratory values 5.7% to 6.4%) - If positive, contact patient and discuss results (phone or in-person) within 3- 5 days

Activity Person	Activity or Task
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Counsel and educate patient on prediabetes diagnosis: the health care provider will provide discussion on lifestyle modifications (healthy eating, portion control, physical activity: 30 minutes of exercise 5 days a week, lose identified weight number agreed upon: between patient and provider and enroll patient in diabetes and nutrition class lead by the registered dietician - Schedule meeting at the clinic or conduct a telephone appointment visit (TAV) within 1- week - Recheck HgbA1c laboratory tests at 3- month intervals until HgbA1c laboratory values are 5.6% or lower - Activity to take place in the clinic in the exam room of the clinic if a medical appointment was scheduled or via the telephone if a TAV was scheduled
Health Care Provider (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meet with patient to discuss diagnosis and treatment interventions based on prediabetes algorithm - Instruct nursing staff to schedule appointment with registered dietician for the next upcoming available class or enter order directly in the computer system & the Health education department will contact the prediabetic patient directly - Schedule 90- day “Remind Me” message with patient - Activity to take place in the clinic in the exam room of the clinical setting if a medical appointment was scheduled or via the telephone if a TAV was scheduled
Nursing Staff (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Schedule appointment with dietician (over phone or via computer system) - Activity to take place at the clinic in person if the patient is present or via the phone. If the patient has a TAV with the primary care provider, the health care provider will route a message to the nursing staff to schedule the patient for the diabetes and nutrition class (or the health care provider can do this step directly). The nursing staff in turn is to call the health education department and is to enroll the patient in the diabetes and nutrition class
Dietician or Health Educator (recipient)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meet patient in person (classroom/group setting) - 4- hour meeting (discuss diet, nutrition, exercise) - Also discuss dangers of diabetes and the need to take action now - Meetings are held 2x per week (5pm to 7pm) on Mondays and Wednesdays - Meetings also held 1x per month on Saturday (9am to 2pm) - Patient is provided printed information: booklet given by the dietician on diabetes and nutrition - Patient provided phone number to obtain more information if necessary (health education department, online resources) - Patient has option to meet one- on- one with dietician, which is discussed during the visit with the primary care provider - Dietician/Health Educator will send an electronic message to physician that patient attended/completed the nutrition class one week after completion of class - Author of prediabetes algorithm to meet with registered dietician as needed - Activity will take place in the conference room of the clinic

Table 9

Data Analysis: Patient Participation Assumptions and Calculations

June 2017	July 2017	August 2017	September 2017	October 2017	November 2017	December 2017
Total number of patients seen in clinic per month = 300(e) Assume 75% of patients are adults = 225 (e) Assume 40% are identified as high-risk for prediabetes = 90(e) Assume 40% test positive for prediabetes = 36(e) 36(e) new prediabetic patients per month = 234(e) over the data collection period						
Total patients seen: 300	Total patients seen: 300	Total patients seen: 300	Total patients seen: 300	Total patients seen: 300	Total patients seen: 300	Total patients seen: 300
36 Total Patients Tracked	72 Total Patients Tracked	108 Total Patients Tracked	144 Total Patients Tracked	180 Total Patients Tracked	216 Total Patients Tracked	234 Total Patients Tracked
			June 2017 3-month interval Follow-up			
				July 2017 3-month interval Follow-up		
					August 2017 3-month interval Follow-up	
						September 2017 3-month interval Follow-up

This change in practice project which included implementation of a prediabetes algorithm involved tracking prediabetic participants seen by the author. The participants were cared for using the prediabetes algorithm. The success of the project was determined largely by the quality of the data collected and the accurate analysis of the

data. In order to achieve this goal, a number of data points were collected, measured, and analyzed.

The following data points represent a sampling of the information collected: (1) total number of adult patients at the rural ambulatory clinic, (2) total number of “at-risk” participants identified and screened by the author, (3) total number of screening HgbA1c laboratory blood draws performed by phlebotomists, (4) total number of laboratory tests indicating a diagnosis of prediabetes (e.g., HgbA1c laboratory values of 5.7% to 6.4%), (5) total number of participant follow-ups with health care provider, (6) total number of participants who attended the prediabetes/ nutrition classes, (7) 3-month participants metrics (i.e., HgbA1c laboratory value, blood pressure reading, weight and BMI measurements).

Objectives of the project were the following: (1) the participants HgbA1c laboratory value would improve at the 3-month interval after making the recommended changes (prediabetes class attendance, lifestyle modifications such as engaging in physical activity and changing diet) and (2) laboratory results at the 3-month interval were the same or lower than the initial HgbA1c laboratory test result (e.g., HgbA1c laboratory value would not increase/worsen).

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic variables of the sample population. Mean, median, and standard deviation were identified for nominal data. Parametric and nonparametric inferential statistics were also carried out in this project. The paired samples *t* test was utilized to compare the baseline HgbA1c laboratory value and the 3-month follow-up HgbA1c laboratory value after the participant made the recommended changes. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was also performed to

examine differences between HgbA1c laboratory values between those participants who attended the prediabetes/nutrition class and those participants which engaged in physical activity. Correlation analyses which included the Pearson's r , Spearman's ρ , and Kendall's tau b correlation coefficients were analyzed to determine whether any associations or relationships could be identified between a decrease in HgbA1c laboratory value and prediabetes class attendance, physical activity, and diet change.

RESULTS

The research question for this project was whether the HgbA1c laboratory value would improve among prediabetic participants at the 3-month follow-up intervals if the author (facilitator) of this project provided an intervention. The intervention consisted of: (1) providing counseling/ education on prediabetes to the participant (in the clinic or via telephone), (2) participant enrolled in the prediabetes nutrition class, and (3) encouraged each participant to engage in lifestyle modifications such as increasing their physical activity level and changing their diet to include healthier eating habits. In order to test this intervention, 162 participants were included in this project.

A convenience sample of 264 participants from an accessible population presenting to a rural ambulatory care setting for a same day appointment met the inclusion criteria and were entered into this project. However, only 162 participants returned at the 3-month interval to have their HgbA1c laboratory test repeated. As a result, this was the sample population for this project.

Descriptive Statistics

The gender demographics of the participants for this project were 79% female and 21% male. The ethnicity demographics were 83.3% Hispanic (Latino), 9.9% Caucasian (White), 4.9% Filipino, 0.6% Asian, 0.6% African-American, and 0.6% classified as other (see Table 10 and Figure 4).

The participants ranged in age from 24-79 years, with a mean age of 52 years, and a standard deviation of 11.01. Body weight ranged from a minimum of 104.00 pounds to a maximum of 466.00 pounds, with a mean of 175.96 pounds and a standard deviation of 42.95. The body mass index (BMI) ranged from a minimum of 21.26 to a maximum of

Table 10

Descriptive Statistics Summary: Gender and Ethnicity

Variable	Total	%
Gender		
Female	128	79.0%
Male	34	21.0%
TOTALS	162	100.0%
Ethnicity		
Hispanic	135	83.3%
Caucasian	16	9.9%
Filipino	8	4.9%
Asian	1	0.6%
African-American	1	0.6%
Other	1	0.6%
TOTALS	162	100.0%

Figure 4. Gender and ethnicity demographics of participants.

58.36, with a mean of 30.65 and a standard deviation of 6.04. For reference, a BMI between 18.5 and 25 is considered ideal, BMI between 25 and 30 is considered overweight and a BMI over 30 is considered obese (see Table 11).

Table 11

Descriptive Statistics Summary: Age, Weight, and BMI

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Median	<i>N</i>	Minimum	Maximum
Age	52.00	11.01	52.00	162	24.00	79.00
Weight	175.96	42.95	169.00	162	104.00	466.00
BMI	30.65	6.04	29.39	161	21.26	58.36

Prediabetes is defined by a range of HgbA1c laboratory values between 5.7% and 6.4%. All participants included in the project conformed within this range. The initial (baseline) HgbA1c laboratory value mean was 5.96%, the median was 5.90%, and the standard deviation was 0.204. The follow-up HgbA1c laboratory value occurred at the 3-month interval. For this measurement, the mean HgbA1c laboratory value was 5.6%, the median was 5.6% and the standard deviation was 0.288. The decrease in the HgbA1c laboratory value ranged from a minimum of -0.2% to a maximum of +1.6%. The mean decrease in the HgbA1c laboratory value was 0.314, the median was 0.300 and the standard deviation was 0.235 (see Table 12).

Table 12

Descriptive Statistics: Participants Change in HgbA1c Laboratory Values

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Median	<i>N</i>	Minimum	Maximum
Baseline HgbA1c	5.964	0.204	5.900	162	5.700	6.400
3-month HgbA1c	5.650	0.288	5.600	162	4.200	6.400
Decrease HgbA1c	0.314	0.235	0.300	162	-0.200	1.600

The change in HgbA1c laboratory value at the 3-month follow-up mark was as follows: (1) 87.7 % of the participants had an improvement in their HgbA1c laboratory value. Meaning their HgbA1c laboratory value decreased from their baseline HgbA1c laboratory value, decreasing the progression into diabetes mellitus type II, (2) 8.6% of the participants did not have any type of change in their HgbA1c laboratory value. Meaning their baseline HgbA1c laboratory value was the same at the 3-month follow-up mark, and (3) 3.7% of the participants HgbA1c laboratory value worsened. That is, their HgbA1c laboratory value worsened, getting closer to the realm of diabetes mellitus type II (see Table 13). A visual representation of these findings is also included in this project (see Figure 5).

Table 13

Change in HgbA1c Laboratory Value Baseline to 3-Month Follow-Up

Variable	Total	%
HgbA1c laboratory value:		
Improvement	142	87.7%
No Change	14	8.6%
Worsened	6	3.7%
TOTALS	162	100.0%

Figure 5. Change in HgbA1c laboratory value baseline to 3-month follow-up.

As indicated in Table 14, titled Interventions there were three independent variables: (1) prediabetes class attendance, (2) engagement in physical activity, and (3) dietary changes to include healthier eating. The total number of participants for this project (n) was 162. From this total, 127 participants provided a yes/no telephonic response to the independent variable questions and 35 participants did not respond (not able to directly speak with participants). With respect to the prediabetes class attendance, 37 participants (22.8%) attended and 90 participants (55.6%) did not attend. An additional 35 participants (21.6%) were unable to be reached to provide a response. As it related to engaging in physical activity, 117 participants (72.2%) engaged in this lifestyle modification and 10 participants (6.2%) did not. An additional 35 participants (21.6%) were unable to be reached to provide a response.

Table 14

Interventions

Independent Variables	YES		NO		No Response		<i>N</i>
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	
Interventions:							
Attended Prediabetes Class	37	22.8%	90	55.6%	35	21.6%	162
Engaged in Physical Activity	117	72.2%	10	6.2%	35	21.6%	162
Changed Diet (Healthy Eating)	125	77.2%	2	1.2%	35	21.6%	162

As it related to change in diet, 125 participants (77.2%) engaged in this lifestyle modification and 2 participants (1.2%) did not. An additional 35 participants (21.6%) were unable to be reached to provide a response.

The primary question of the project focused on the extent to which prediabetes outcomes could be improved through counseling, education, and engagement in lifestyle modifications (i.e., physical activity and healthier eating habits). Two outcomes were possible: (1) there would be no difference in the HgbA1c laboratory value before and after the intervention or (2) the participants' HgbA1c laboratory values would improve at the 3-month follow-up due to counseling, education, engaging in physical activity and change in diet (healthier eating habits). A paired samples *t* test was performed to analyze whether the participant's HgbA1c laboratory value improved at 3-month follow-up interval. The independent variables were the baseline HgbA1c laboratory value and the 3-month follow-up HgbA1c laboratory value. The dependent variable was the HgbA1c laboratory value.

Based on the results of this statistical analysis, the participants' HgbA1c laboratory value improved at the 3-month follow-up due to counseling, education, engagement in physical activity and dietary changes (healthier eating habits). The *p* value

was 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicating there was statistical significance for the participants involved in the intervention (see Table 15).

Table 15

Paired Samples t Test and Descriptive Statistics for Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value and 3-Month HgbA1c Laboratory Value

	Baseline A1c		3-Month A1c		<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Significant
	<i>M</i>	(<i>SD</i>)	<i>M</i>	(<i>SD</i>)				
A1c Dependent Variable	5.964	(0.204)	5.650	(0.288)	17.000	161	0.000	Yes

A second aspect of the project was to look at the specific effect of taking a prediabetes class with the HgbA1c laboratory variable. For example, would there be a change or a significant difference in the HgbA1c laboratory variable in HgbA1c laboratory values among those participants who took the prediabetes class and those who did not take the prediabetes class. Also, it was anticipated that those who attended the prediabetes class led by a registered dietician or diabetes educator would have a greater change in the HgbA1c laboratory value than those who did not take the prediabetes class. The statistical analysis carried out for this inquiry was a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). It was performed to determine whether the difference between the two HgbA1c laboratory values were different between those who attended the class and those who did not attend the class. The independent variable was the prediabetes class attendance by the participant.

The dependent variable was the difference between the baseline HgbA1c laboratory value and the 3-month HgbA1c laboratory value follow-up. Based on the results of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), there was no change in the variable difference between HgbA1c laboratory values between those who took the

prediabetes class and those who did not take the prediabetes class. The p value was 0.344, which is greater than 0.05, indicating there was no statistical significance between participants who attended the prediabetes class and those who did not, $F(1, 125) = 0.903$, $p = 0.344$ (see Table 16).

Table 16

ANOVA: Prediabetes Class Attendance and HgbA1c Laboratory Value

	YES			NO			F	df	p	Significant
	M	(SD)	N	M	(SD)	N				
Attended Class	0.378	(0.206)	37	0.337	(0.232)	90	0.903	1, 125	0.344	No

Note. DV = Difference in HgbA1c Laboratory Value.

The third area examined was the specific effect of physical activity on the HgbA1c laboratory value of the participants. Two outcomes were a possibility: (1) those participants who engaged in physical activity would have a greater change in the HgbA1c laboratory value than those who did not engage in physical activity, or (2) there would be no change in the variable difference between HgbA1c laboratory value between those who engaged in physical activity and those who did not.

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was analyzed to determine whether there was a difference between the two HgbA1c laboratory values of those who exercised and those who did not exercise. The independent variable was physical activity (the participant was asked if he/she engaged in physical activity: a yes, or no response was documented). The dependent variable was the difference between the baseline HgbA1c laboratory value and the 3-month follow-up HgbA1c laboratory value. Based on the results of this statistical analysis, those participants who reported having engaged in

physical activity, had a greater change in the HgbA1c laboratory value than those who did not engage in physical activity. The p value was 0.013, which is less than 0.05, indicating there was statistical significance in the HgbA1c laboratory values of participants who engaged in physical activity, $F(1, 125) = 6.394$, $p = 0.013$ (see Table 17).

Table 17

ANOVA: Physical Activity and HgbA1c Laboratory Value

	YES			NO			F	df	p	Significant
	M	(SD)	N	M	(SD)	N				
Physical Activity	0.363	(0.217)	117	0.180	(0.253)	10	6.390	1, 125	0.013	Yes

Note. DV = Difference in HgbA1c laboratory value.

A statistical analysis of the independent variable, diet change was not performed as 98.4% of the participants (125 out of 127 respondents) reported having changed their diet. Only two participants reported not making any dietary changes.

Correlation analysis was utilized to evaluate whether there was a (1) relationship between a change in HgbA1c laboratory value and prediabetes class attendance, (2) a relationship between a change in HgbA1c laboratory value and engaging in physical activity, and (3) a relationship between a change in HgbA1c laboratory value and changing diet (healthier eating habits).

Parametric Correlation: Pearson's r

There was a correlation/relationship between a decrease in HgbA1c laboratory value and having engaged in physical activity, which is consistent with the findings obtained with the one-way ANOVA analysis (see Table 18).

Table 18

Means and Correlation Matrix (Pearson's r)

	Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value	3-Month HgbA1c Laboratory Value	Decrease HgbA1c Laboratory Value	Physical Activity	Attended Class
Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value	1.0	0.593**	0.142	0.046	0.156
3-Month HgbA1c Laboratory Value		1.0	-0.714**	-0.145	-0.043
Decrease HgbA1c Laboratory Value			1.0	0.221**	0.085
Physical Activity				1.0	0.123
Attended Class					1.0

* Denotes correlation with significance of $p < .05$.

** Denotes correlation with significance of $p < .001$.

Nonparametric Correlation (Spearman's ρ)

The results in this correlation matrix are similar to the Pearson's r findings, with the exception of Spearman's ρ exhibiting a lower level of significance between physical activity and a decrease in HgbA1c laboratory values (see Table 19).

Table 19

Means and Correlation Matrix (Spearman's rho)

	Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value	3-Month HgbA1 Laboratory Value	Decrease HgbA1c Laboratory Value	Physical Activity	Attended Class
Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value	1.0	0.584**	0.197*	-0.021	0.165
3-Month HgbA1c Laboratory Value		1.0	-0.637**	0.082	0.004
Decrease HgbA1c Laboratory Value			1.0	0.186*	0.144
Physical Activity				1.0	0.123
Attended Class					1.0

* Denotes correlation with significance of $p < .05$.

** Denotes correlation with significance of $p < .001$.

Nonparametric Correlation (Kendall's tau b)

The results in this correlation matrix were similar to the findings obtained in the previous correlation coefficients (Pearson's r and Spearman's rho; see Table 20).

Table 20

Means and Correlation Matrix (Kendall's tau b)

	Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value	3-Month HgbA1c Laboratory Value	Decrease HgbA1c Laboratory Value	Physical Activity	Attended Class
Baseline HgbA1c Laboratory Value	1.0	0.467**	0.155*	0.043	0.144
3-Month HgbA1c Laboratory Value		1.0	-0.497**	0.070	0.004
Decrease HgbA1c Laboratory Value			1.0	0.162*	0.126
Physical Activity				1.0	0.123
Attended Class					1.0

* Denotes correlation with significance of $p < .05$.

** Denotes correlation with significance of $p < .001$.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this scholarly project was to evaluate a change in practice by implementing a prediabetes intervention. The goal of the project was to determine whether the intervention would assist participants in decreasing HgbA1c laboratory values and prevent progression from a prediabetes diagnosis into a diabetes mellitus type II diagnosis. By carrying out this project and obtaining the statistically significant results, the findings support that a consistent approach to prediabetes can be implemented within a clinic setting and with all primary health care providers. This approach is similar to common protocols employed for the treatment of hypertension and diabetes mellitus type II. Doing so, has the potential to improve patient health and lower the cost of treatment.

The results of this project indicate 87.7% of the participants ($n = 142$) had a decrease in their HgbA1c laboratory value at the 3-month follow-up. This represented an average HgbA1c laboratory value decrease of 0.314% after a single intervention and 90-120 days of time. These findings are statistically significant and were validated with a paired samples t test. Statistical significance was also achieved with a one-way ANOVA for physical activity. Those participants who responded “yes” (meaning they had engaged in physical activity during the time period of the project), demonstrated a significantly greater decrease in HgbA1c laboratory than those who did not.

In contrast, no statistical significance was demonstrated among participants who attended the prediabetes class. From the total population of participants ($n = 162$), 37 attended the class, 90 did not attend the class and 35 did not respond. Additionally, no statistical significance was achieved between participants who engaged in dietary changes and a decrease of the HgbA1c laboratory value at the 3-month follow-up.

Recommendations

The project was conducted in a rural ambulatory care setting, out of a need to address prediabetes. The recommendations from this project will be shared with management and primary health care providers. The objective is to obtain approval to implement the innovation over a longer period of time (i.e., 12 months) and to have all primary health care providers in the clinic address prediabetes in a systematic and consistent manner. The positive, conclusive findings of this project will be presented to management as a way to improve patient health and lower the cost of providing care.

This project focused on the identification of patients with risk factors for prediabetes/diabetes mellitus type II. The patients with risk factors were screened by ordering a HgbA1c laboratory test. The prediabetes diagnosis was made based on the HgbA1c laboratory value (5.7% to 6.4%) and the identified patient with prediabetes was provided with early intervention treatment. During the project, a significant number of the population experienced a lowering of the HgbA1c laboratory value, thus decreasing the progression of diabetes mellitus type II. Thus, patient health improved. Also, the cost of providing care to the patient at this stage is a fraction of the cost of leaving the patient un-informed and risking the further development of diabetes mellitus type II.

The first step to implementation is management approval. Approval will be obtained by reinforcing the statistically significant results obtained from a simple change in practice. Thereafter, an implementation and feasibility plan will be developed and shared with the other primary health care providers in the clinic.

A new extended project would be based on the original innovation but incorporate additional resources to address the limitations identified in this project. It is important to

stay abreast of developments outside of the organization. An example of this is the 2017 decision within the California Senate (SB-97), that Medi-Cal will provide coverage for Diabetes Prevention Programs (DPP) initiatives.

The framework incorporated in this project was the i-PARIHS model (Integration and Promoting Action Research in Health Sciences). This evidence-based framework emphasizes the importance of translating knowledge into evidence and then transferring this knowledge into the clinical setting. The key mechanism of action in this model is facilitation. The project results indicate at-risk patients are willing and able to make needed lifestyle modifications during a short period of time. As indicated in the results, 87.7% of the participants ($n = 142$), were able to obtain a reduction in HgbA1c laboratory value within 90-120 days. This suggests there is an opportunity to expand the project to other settings, where information on the risks of prediabetes can be delivered. Within the existing clinic, patient waiting rooms include a TV; however, it is powered off. The TV should be connected to a video feed, which provides information on prediabetes health risks, as well as the impact that even simple lifestyle choices can lower risks.

General public awareness is needed in order for society to have a better understanding of how daily decisions and choices impact long-term health. Recommendations going forward include development of a program, which would identify how easy and affordable it can be to eat healthy, as well as the benefits of exercise. This information is not currently shared with the general public in a manner which can be useful and assists in explaining the health crisis that currently exists with prediabetes.

A final recommendation is the establishment of a prediabetes specialist role at the primary care practice level. Any and all patients with risk factors should be referred to this specialist for consultation and evaluation.

Limitations of the Project

The primary limitation of the project was a single provider implementing the outreach and compiling the data. This resulted in fewer phone calls being made to re-connect with participants after the initial HgbA1c laboratory results. Although all participants received at least one contact, requesting the participant to return for a 3-month follow-up laboratory testing, additional contacts may have resulted in a greater number of patients returning. An additional limitation included the timing and offering of days of the prediabetes nutrition class. The belief is that greater numbers of participants would have attended the class had it been offered more frequently, at different locations, and on a variety of dates and times.

Patient follow-up at the 3-month interval did not capture weight, BMI and blood pressure. This presented gaps in project data, which would have provided additional insight had the data been available. A final limitation was the inability to obtain explicit details from participants on the types and amounts of lifestyle modifications implemented. Additional data, would provide targeted feedback which could then be shared with other participants. An example being that major lifestyle changes are not necessarily needed. Small, consistent changes over time can achieve positive outcomes for participants.

Implications for Practice

According to the CDC (2017), more than 84 million American adults have prediabetes. More importantly, 90% of individuals with prediabetes are unaware they have it. Without intervention and lifestyle modifications, up to 30% of individuals with prediabetes will develop type II diabetes within 5 years (Babey et al., 2016). This would suggest an additional 25.2 million new individuals would be diagnosed with diabetes as early as 2023. This has the potential to create substantial chronic diseases in every clinic within the US. Left untreated, the prediabetes crisis could contribute to a failure of the health care system to provide needed and effective care.

Fortunately, prediabetes can be treated and reversed. However, it will require a change in the way health care systems currently approach this medical condition. Projects such as this one suggest that even minimal interventions over very short periods of time can achieve positive results. However, to achieve these results an awareness of the problem must exist and a common set of strategies must be in place. This does not require a cumbersome rebuild of existing policies and procedures. Nor does it require health care organizations to expend millions of dollars in new facilities and equipment. Instead, a simple program utilizing basic strategies by health care providers can make a dramatic difference in prevention.

The solution begins with identifying at-risk patients, having discussions with them and receiving buy-in with three minimal changes: (1) 90-day HgbA1c laboratory testing, (2) prediabetes education, and (3) simple lifestyle changes related to exercise and diet. It is vital patients be provided information and education needed in order for them to make better lifestyle decisions. It is equally important health care providers become more

aware of risk factors and be willing to intervene and assist patients in understanding the risks they face.

SUMMARY

Prediabetes is a growing health care problem and concern. However, unlike other chronic diseases, prediabetes is preventable, treatable and reversible. There are no expensive drugs required, invasive surgical procedures or visits to numerous specialists. Instead, the solution to this health crisis, which currently impacts 84 million American adults, is relatively simple and consists of two fundamental phases.

The first phase requires health care providers to become more aware and educated on the health care problem of prediabetes and to implement needed programs to identify and treat at risk patients. The second phase includes the education/counseling of at risk patients and their participation in lifestyle modifications, such as physical activity and healthy eating habits. As this project has proven, clinically and statistically significant results are achievable even with one health care provider and a relatively simple innovation deployed in a small patient population in a rural ambulatory clinic.

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APPENDIX A

PERMISSION TO USE i-PARIHS MODEL

Permission To Use The iPARIHS Model Inbox x

to gillian.harvey, gillharvey

Dr Harvey,

I am working on my scholarly project and will also be submitting a manuscript for publication. I would like your permission to use the iPARIHS model and the corresponding figure in these projects.

Thank you for your consideration.

Respectfully,
Lupe Yopez-Michel, RN
DNP Candidate

to me

Hi Lupe – yes very happy for you to use this image.
Good luck with your manuscript.
Best wishes
Gill

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APPENDIX B
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Prediabetes Treatment Interventions

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Carry out a comprehensive review on cost effectiveness of lifestyle interventions by examining the type of intervention: dietician vs. no dietician & method of delivery: in person vs. technology delivery (Sun et al., 2017)	Systematic review & meta-analysis: RCT (<i>n</i> = 41), pre-post (<i>n</i> = 25), matched cohort design (<i>n</i> = 2), nonrandomized comparison (<i>n</i> = 1) IV: Intervention delivery agent: Dietician & channel (in person vs technology delivery) DV: Weight changes, BG concentrations, HbA1c, cost	69 studies: 32 conducted in the United States & 37 in other countries	Vary by study (body weight, BMI, FBG, 2-Hr BG, HbA1c)	Weight (64 studies): overall effect size negative (CIs significant for different weight sizes) FBG (41 studies) average effect size negative (CIs varied by time) 2-Hr BG (19 studies) & HbA1c (15 studies): overall effect size negative: 2-Hr BG, magnitude increased to 0.6; HbA1c, effect sizes negative, greatest magnitude 0.34 @ 12 months Intervention Cost (8 studies): average intervention cost/	Conclusion: Outcomes all significantly better with treatment Limitations: Missing values & method of handling withdrawals could have been improved upon Cost, cost effectiveness information was limited A # of studies did not report confounder adjusted outcomes Notes: Relevant to goal of utilizing registered dieticians to provide diet education to the

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				participant (5 studies) \$385	population of interest (prediabetes)
				Dietician delivered interventions had the largest & statistically significant average effect size on weight reduction at 3 months ($p < 0.001$) & at 12 months ($p = 0.025$)	
Examine cost effectiveness: standard care group vs. structured education program (Leal et al., 2017)	Randomized control trial IV: Structured education intervention program DV: Cost, QOL, resource use	880 patients randomized to receive either standard of care OR a 6-hr. group structured education program with FU sessions in a primary care setting 447 IG 433 SCG 44 general practices in Leicestershire, England	Incremental cost utility from the NHS perspective QOL resource measure from baseline & during 36 mo. f/u using the Euro-QOL EQ-5D & 15D instruments & an economic questionnaire Outcomes measured using quality adjusted life years (QALYs) & health costs calculated in 2012-2103 prices	The IG was found to have a net gain of 0.046 (CI 95%) in QALYs over 3 years The incremental cost effectiveness was measured in Euros with an 86% probability of being cost effective	Conclusion(s): Structured education program was more expensive & was associated with a higher QOL 3-year f/u is considered appropriate to assess cost-effectiveness Limitations: Missing data, attrition in patient responses to questionnaires Incremental cost effectiveness ratio is reported in pounds

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
					Notes: Relevant to DNP project
Examine effect of an algorithm-driven online DPP on changes in eating habits, physical activity & wellness/ productivity factors (Block et al., 2016)	Randomized controlled trial IV: IG (Alive-PD) vs. CG DV: BW, FG & HbA1c	1 CBC 339 prediabetic patients 163 IG 176 CG Study time period dates not provided Palo Alto, California	IG included (1) detailed diet/activity questionnaire, (2) wellness/productivity questions, (3) weekly goal setting, (4) tracking, (5) team system for social support & (6) six summary questions (eating & PA) Entire program is delivered via web, email, & IVR. All participant contact automated & algorithm driven (no personal contact or coaching) CG: six summary questions (eating & PA) Measures are self-reported & include changes in following: (1) PA & (2) food habits & (3) wellness/productivity Baseline demographics	69% male, 31% female, mean age 55, 68% white, mean BMI = 31 95% = prediabetes by FG 45% = prediabetes by HbA1c 68.1% = metabolic syndrome 6-month results: IG: Fruit/vegetable consumption ↑ 3.71x per week. R-CHO ↓ 3.77x per week. ↑ in PA, self-rated health & confidence to make dietary changes. CG: Fruit/vegetable consumption ≠ Δ. Lower improvements in PA, self-rated health & confidence to make dietary changes.	Conclusions: Alive-PD = improved eating habits & PA. Promotes improvements in weight, glycemic markers, wellness/ productivity variables & self-rated health status Limitations: Diet & activity changes self-reported Response rate to online diet/activity questionnaire (CG = 84%, IG = 62%) Notes: Partially applicable; technology allows outreach to more participants Consider a hybrid approach that combines

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			Clinical assessment at baseline, 3-months, & 6-months		personal & virtual contact
Determine if commercial weight management program (WW) could achieve sufficient weight loss in persons with prediabetes compared to a DPP (Marrero et al., 2016)	Randomized control trial IV: WW vs. DPP (WW = IG, DPP = CG) DV: Primary: BW Secondary: BP, HbA1c, total cholesterol & HDL-c	8 CBS 225 persons with prediabetes 112 WW 113 DPP Study time period 2013 to 2014 Indianapolis, Indiana	WW included (1) 45-minute activation session with trained coaches, (2) enrollment in existing WW program at convenient locations/times, (3) encouragement & (4) access to all WW e-tools & services/sessions DPP included (1) 15-minute individual counselling session with trained research staff, (2) weight loss review & education materials & (3) tracker to help monitor food intake & booklet with fat/calorie information for common foods Measures includes changes in following (1) BW, (2) BP, (3) HbA1c, (4) total cholesterol, & (5) HDL-c Baseline demographics	15% male, 85% female. Average age = 52 (<i>SD</i> = 11). White = 64%. BMI = 36.8 (<i>SD</i> = 7.1). Baseline BW = 100.63 kg (<i>SD</i> = 20.8) 12-month results: WW BW (kg) = ↓ 5.55 BP = ↓ 3.30 (systolic) HbA1c = ↓ 0.25% Total Cholesterol = ↑ 0.45 HDL-c = ↑ 6.29 DPP BW (kg) = ↓ 0.22 BP = ↓ 3.39 (systolic) HbA1c = ↓ 0.18% Total Cholesterol = ↓ 0.61 HDL-c = ↑ 2.99	Conclusions: WW commercial weight loss offers variety of benefits & convenient program features to fight progression of prediabetes Proven weight loss Limitations: Loss of participants to follow-up at 12 months WW funded study > 84% female > 60% undergraduate of higher education > 58% had annual income ≥ \$50,000 Notes: Study reveals innovative approach to

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			Clinical assessment at baseline, 6-months & 12-months		address prediabetes issue. Partnerships with existing companies provides ability to scale quickly
Examine the prevalence & determinants of prediabetes among Mexican adults (Kumar, Wong, Ottenbacher, & Snih, 2016)	Longitudinal study IV: Prevalence & factors associated with prediabetes DV: BMI, central obesity, medical conditions, cholesterol, HDL, HbA1c & Vit. D	2012 participants subsample of the Mexican Health & Aging Study	Logistic regression was performed to ID factors associated with prediabetes	Prevalence of prediabetes was 44.2% Participants with ↑ waist-hip ratio (1.61, 95% CI = 1.05-2.45) & ↑ Chol (1.85, 95% CI = 1.36-2.51) had higher odds of prediabetes Overweight (1.68, 95% CI = 1.07-2.64), obesity (2.38, 95% CI = 1.41-4.02) & ↑ WC (1.60, 95% CI = 1.06-2.40) were significantly associated with ↑ odds of having undiagnosed DM Participants engaged in regular PA had ↓ lower odds of undiagnosed DM (0.74, 95% CI = 0.57-0.97)	Conclusion: High # of people who have prediabetes & undiagnosed DM among adults who are Mexican, resources are needed to prevent. ID & treat this population Limitations: Cross sectional data from 2012 Subsample from the larger sample was interviewed which limits generalizability Notes: Relevant to DNP project, as this is the identified population

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Determine feasibility of implementing a large scale primary care DM prevention trial (Dawes et al., 2015)	Randomized controlled trial	6 FP	FLIP included (1) lifestyle advice, (2) a pedometer & (3) telephone support from lifestyle facilitator	51% male, 49% female, 53% ≥ 65 years of age. 69% Caucasian, 29% Asian, 2% Hispanics	Conclusions: A1C & BP Δ's not statistically significant
	IV: FLIP vs. CG (FLIP = IG) DV: Preventing diabetes progression	59 prediabetic patients 35 IG 24 CG	CG: usual care from FPP	41% existing HTN	IG had ↓ in weight, BMI, WC & EE vs. CG
		Study time period October 2012 to March 2013 British Columbia, Canada	Measures include changes in following (1) differences in A1C levels from baseline to 6-months, (2) weight, (3) WC & (4) EE Baseline demographics Clinical assessment at baseline & 6-months	6-month results: IG: At 6-months: 0.07% ↓ in A1C levels (<i>SD</i> = 0.21) CG: At 6-months: 0.03% ↑ in A1C levels (<i>SD</i> = 0.24) During study, 2 patients from CG registered A1C level > 6.5%	Trial design feasible Positive trends in outcomes (mean differences in HbA1c & ↓ in weight) Limitations: Study not powered to show statistically significant differences Adjustment for clustering Study duration too short Notes: Relevant to goal of designing & implementing a “FLIP-like” study at current place of employment
Examine the rationale, design	Three-arm randomized control trial	92 participants	Baseline demographics	Baseline differences across the 3 treatment	Conclusion:

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
& baseline characteristics of the PREVENT-DM study (Perez et al., 2015)	IV: Standard care group (SCG) DPP-based lifestyle intervention Metformin medication DV: (Primary) differences in weight@ 12 months (Secondary) changes in cardio metabolic markers: BMI, WC, BP, FPG, Hba1c, Total CHOL, Trig, HDL, LDL	Philadelphia PA Clinic partner sites & community-based venues	Clinical assessment at baseline, 6 & 12 months Psychosocial measures: -health literacy -health related QOL -acculturation -social support -perceived stress -depression -anxiety	arms were examined using one analysis of variance (ANOVA) Future manuscripts will report on 12-month study outcomes	One third of the U.S. population has prediabetes, yet only 10% of those affected are aware of their prediabetes diagnosis HCP do not uniformly offer lifestyle counseling to this population & they do not prescribe metformin medication Limitations: Final results not reported Resource limitations (one full time staff member) Only female Latinas were recruited, limiting generalizability Small sample Notes: Highly relevant to DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Examine the utilization of metformin on prediabetes patients (Moin et al., 2015)	Retrospective cohort study IV: Metformin rx DV: Delay progression to DM	17,352 working age adults Employer groups that purchased health plans from nation's largest insurer (United Healthcare)	Percentage of health plan enrollees with prediabetes who were prescribed metformin over a 3-year period	3.7% of patients ($n = 647$) with prediabetes were prescribed metformin over the 3-year study period Among a smaller subset of patients with a BMI ≥ 35 ($n = 391$) or gestation DM ($n = 121$): (2 groups for which the ADA guidelines place an effort for treating prediabetes with metformin), the prevalence for the metformin prescription was 7.8% Predicted probability of metformin rx was 2 times as high among women (4.8%) than among men (2.8%; $p < 0.001$)	Conclusion: Study reports metformin medication is not routinely prescribed for prediabetes, yet it is considered, safe, tolerable, evidence based & cost effective in the management of prediabetes Limitations: Missing data on lifestyle interventions Possible misclassification of prediabetes & metformin use Notes: Findings highly relevant to DNP project
Investigate effect of MNT in obese adults with prediabetes	A prospective, randomized, parallel group design IV: MNT vs. UC (MNT = IG, UC = CG)	Anaheim Clinical Trials 76 adults with prediabetes 41 MNT	MNT included (1) four visits with RDN. First visit = 60-minutes. Subsequent visits range from 30-45 minutes each, (2) self-management training for diet & physical	26.3% male, 73.6% female, mean age > 49.61 years. 88% white of which 42% were Hispanic. Mean BMI > 33.06. Mean WC (cm) > 106.89	Conclusions: MNT can lead to improvement in metabolic control Limitations:

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
(Parker, Byham-Gray, Denmark, & Winkle, 2014)	DV: Primary: FPG Secondary: HbA1c, total cholesterol, HDL-c & DRS	35 UC Study time period April-2010 to May-2011 Anaheim, CA, & nearby communities	activity, (3) pedometer & (4) DRC questionnaire UC: DRC questionnaire Measures included (1) FPG, (2) HbA1c, (3) total cholesterol, (4) HDL-c & (5) DRS Baseline demographics Clinical assessment at baseline & 12-weeks	<u>12-week results:</u> <u>MNT</u> FPG = ↓ 1.66 HbA1c = ↓ 0.19 Total CHOL = ↓ 10.22 HDL-c = ↓ 0.02 DRS = ↓ 2.22 <u>UC</u> FPG = ↓ 1.97 HbA1c = ↑ 0.05 Total CHOL = ↓ 3.69 HDL-c = ↑ 1.23 DRS = ↓ 0.40	Pilot study of 12 weeks. Study was conducted at single clinical site. Patients perceptions, characteristics, income levels, influence of practice styles, may have been limitations Notes: Useful & significant findings with respect to use of RDN. This study is relevant to my goal of designing & implementing a “MNT-like” study at current place of employment
Summarize the effectiveness of translational (translate results from previous trials) DPP, as a result of lifestyle changes designed to prevent type II diabetes. Thereafter, review results to determine if	Systematic review & Meta-analysis IV: Lifestyle interventions (dietary, PA or both) DV: Weight loss, changes in BMI, FG, 2Hr-BG, HbA1c, total CHOL, HDL, Trig, SBP, DBP	<i>n</i> = 25 studies for systematic review. US (<i>n</i> = 11), Australia (<i>n</i> = 2), Europe (<i>n</i> = 11), Japan (<i>n</i> = 1). <i>n</i> = 22 studies for meta-analysis Leicester, UK	Vary by study	Lifestyle interventions resulted in mean weight loss of 2.12 kg (95% CI) over 12 months Adherence to international guidelines indicated greater weight loss	Conclusion: Meta-analysis revealed mean weight loss of 2.1 kg at 12-month f/u. Also observed reduction in blood glucose, BP & some cholesterol measures Limitations: Insufficient data to analyze outcomes beyond 12 months

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
adherence to international guidelines is consistent with effectiveness (Dunkley et al., 2014)					Notes: Analysis was restricted to intervention arms only Findings relevant to DNP project

APPENDIX C
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Diabetes Prevention Programs

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Examine the effectiveness of DPP in Hispanics in lowering risk for type 2 DM by lowering weight or improving glucose regulation (McCurley et al., 2017)	Systematic review	12 studies	Vary by study	Interventions varied in length, rigor & tailoring strategies	Conclusion: Culturally tailored diabetes prevention interventions for Hispanics appear to be modestly effective in decreasing the risk for DM 2
	IV: DPP	5 RCTs		9 studies reported significant changes in weight loss	
	DV: Changes in weight, glucose regulation	6 single group pre-post uncontrolled trials		2 noted changes in glucose regulation	Limitations: Inclusion of small, uncontrolled trials of moderate to low quality
		1 quasi experimental community comparison group		Effect sizes were small to moderate	
				Study quality was moderate	Some completed interventions may not have been included due to publication bias
				Attrition was high in most trials	
				Interventions with the highest effect sizes: -literacy modification	Lack of generalizability
					Exclusive use of self-report

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				-Hispanic foods/recipes -cultural DM beliefs -family/friend participation structured community input innovative experiential learning	Notes: Findings relevant to DNP project
Examine data from programs based on implementation of the DPP in different settings & combine these findings into a large analysis & understand if such programs were associated with changes in weight, blood sugars, blood pressure, & cholesterol (Mudaliar et al., 2016)	Systematic review & meta-analysis IV: DPP DV: Weight changes, FBG, HbA1c, SBP, DBP, HDL, TC	44 U.S. community-based studies 22 single group pre-post designs 3 studies with 2 interventions arms 18 studies separate control arms 1 study with 3 arms (2 intervention groups & 1 control)	Vary by study	Across all studies pre-post weight change was -3.77 kg (95% CI:-4.55to 2.99) 8 studies measured HbA1c, mean pre-post change was -0.21% (95% CI: -0.29; -0.31) 21 studies reported FBG, mean change was -2.40mg/dl (95% CI:-3.59;-1.21) 23 studies evaluated BP, mean pre-post change in SBP of -4.29 mmHg (95% CI:-5.73, -2.84, & -2.56 mm Hg in DBP (95% CI: -3.40,1.17)	Conclusion: Lifestyle programs following the principles of the DPP in clinic & community-based settings are effective in reducing weight, FBG, HgA1c, at the 1-year mark Limitations: Heterogeneity of the studies Differences in duration in FU Lack of statistical significance in stratified analyses

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				No statistical significant differences in risk factors when comparing studies testing interventions by CWs to studies that used employed health professionals	Study confined to previously reported results Notes: Relevant to DNP project
Evaluate impact of a worksite DPP (Miller et al., 2016)	Randomized controlled trial Pretest-posttest control group design with 3-month follow-up IV: EG vs. CG (EG = IG) DV: BW & AHEI Score	University work site 68 adults with prediabetes 35 IG/EG 33 CG Study time period dates not provided Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio	EG included (1) single 60-minute group session per week by lifestyle coach for 16 weeks, (2) written manual with session material, (3) food, (4) PA trackers for self-monitoring, (5) graph for tracking weekly BW, (6) booklet with nutrient content of most commonly consumed foods, & (7) encouraged to record calories & fat grams consumed CG: Information booklet regarding lifestyle changes for DM prevention Measures included: (1) BW & (2) AHEI Score Baseline demographics	20.5% male, 79.5% female, 100% > 50 years of age. 82.4% white, 17.6% Black or Asian. > 64% undergraduate or higher education 7-month results: EG BW = ↓ 5.20% AHEI Score = ↑ 1.91 CG BW ↓ 0.21% AHEI Score = ↑ 1.08	Conclusions: Work site intervention resulted in improvements for BW & diet quality Limitations: Small sample size University setting, not representative of general population Study duration Notes: Parts of the study design can be incorporated into planned DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			Clinical assessment at baseline, 4 & 7-months		
Identify critical success factors for implementing DPP in real world settings (Aziz et al., 2015)	Systematic review IV: DPP DV: Program penetration, program implementation, program participation, program effectiveness	38 studies	Vary by study	<p>92% of the studies provided details on participation</p> <p>18 % reported on the coverage of their target population (penetration)</p> <p>Program intensity (implementation) measured by frequency of contacts during the first year & intervention duration was identified in all of the studies</p> <p>84% of the studies reported implementation fidelity</p> <p>18% of studies used quality assurance measures</p> <p>16 & 26% of the studies reported high or</p>	<p>Conclusion: Program intensity is a major contributor in weight reduction</p> <p>Limitations: Several studies did not provide relevant numeric data to calculate PIPE coefficients, therefore unable to compare the overall program impact of included studies</p> <p>Notes: Findings relevant to DNP project</p>

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				<p>moderate positive changes respectively based on weight loss</p> <p>6 (16%) of the studies reported high DM risk reduction but low to moderate weight loss</p>	
<p>Examine the long-term extent of beneficial effects of lifestyle interventions & metformin on diabetes prevention & whether DM associated microvascular complications are reduced</p> <p>(Nathan et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Randomized control trial</p> <p>IV: Intensive lifestyle interventions or masked metformin with placebo</p> <p>DV: Reduce diabetes development & microvascular complications</p>	<p>3,149 participants in 27 centers across the US</p>	<p>The aggregate microvascular outcomes were analyzed with global testing using (GEE)</p> <p>The study was powered based on the global test</p> <p>Each of the 2 pairwise comparisons (ILS vs placebo & metformin vs placebo) were set at $\alpha = 0.025$ to maintain an overall $\alpha 0.05$ for multiple comparison using Bonferroni adjustment</p> <p>Fixed effects models were used to assess differences in body weight</p>	<p>15 years of average FU, lifestyle interventions & Metformin use reduced DM incidence rate by 27% ($p < 0.0001$) & 18% ($p = 0.001$) respectively</p> <p>The prevalence at study end of the aggregate microvascular outcome (nephropathy, neuropathy & retinopathy) were not significantly different among the treatment group</p>	<p>Conclusion: Lifestyle interventions & metformin use significantly reduce the development of DM over 15 years</p> <p>Limitations: Therapeutic cross over through the offering of lifestyle change instruction to all 3 group during the 1-year bridge period</p> <p>The application of the lifestyle intervention after the first 24 weeks of DPP & during DPPOS was less intense</p> <p>Notes:</p>

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
					Relevant to DNP project
Evaluate 2 adapted DPP lifestyle interventions among overweight or obese adults with prediabetes in a primary care clinic (Ma et al., 2013)	Randomized Control Trial IV: DPP DV: Changes in BMI & cardio metabolic risk factors	241 participants 81 usual care group 79 E-LITE coach led group 81 self-directed DVD intervention group 1 primary clinic Los Altos, California	Trained research assistants who were unaware of participants group assignment carried out anthropometric & BP measurements using standard protocols @ baseline, 3, 6 & 15 months At all-time points except at month 3, blood samples were taken fasting Possible adverse events were assessed by questionnaire @ each f/u visit	At baseline: BMI was 32, 47% were female 78% non-Hispanic white, 17% Asian/Pacific Islander At month 15: Mean ± SE change in BMI from baseline was -2.2±0.3 in the coach led group vs -0.9±0.3 in the usual care group ($p < .001$) & -1.6±0.3 in the self-directed group vs usual care ($p = .02$) The % of participants who achieved the 7% DPP based weight loss goal was 37.0% ($p = .003$) & 35.69% ($p = .004$) in the coach led & self-directed groups respectively vs. 14.4% in the usual care group	Conclusion: DPP Lifestyle interventions are effective in a primary care setting Limitations: Participants were primarily of higher socioeconomic background & from a single primary clinic Replacement of missing weights with clinical values recorded in the HER or self-reported weights might introduce bias Trial lasted 15 months Notes: Relevant to DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				Both interventions resulted in greater net improvements in WC & FBG	
Examine impact of 24-month, community based DPP on FBG, I/IR, BW, WC & BMI in 2nd year of follow-up (Katula et al., 2013)	Randomized controlled trial IV: LWL vs. UCC (LWL = IG, UCC = CG) DV: BW, BMI, WC, FBG & I/IR	> 1 CBS 301 participants 151 LWL 150 UCC Data collection: 2007-2011 Data analyses: 2011-2012 Forsyth County, North Carolina	LWL includes (1) weekly group sessions for initial 6-months, (2) sessions coordinated by CHWs, (3) three personalized consultations with RD, (4) group sessions conducted at community sites & (5) scheduled contacts with CHWs UCC includes (1) two individual sessions with RD within initial 3-months & (2) monthly newsletter Measures includes changes in following: (1) BW (2) BMI (3) WC, (4) FBG & (5) I/IR every 6-month interval by trained study staff Baseline demographics	42.5% male, 57.5% female. Age = 57.9 ± 9.5. White = 72.8%, African-American = 24.6%, Other = 1.5% BMI = 32.7 ± 15.5 Glucose (mg/dL) = 105.5 ± 11.3 24-month results: LWL BW (kg) = ↓ 5.57 BMI = ↓ 1.91 WC (cm) = ↓ 4.01 Glucose (mg/dL) = ↓ 2.09 Insulin (μU/mL) = ↓ 4.42 UCC BW (kg) = ↓ 0.79 BMI = ↓ 0.4 WC (cm) = ↓ 0.32	Conclusions: A DPP administered through existing CBS, delivered by CHWs is effective at inducing significant long-term reductions in metabolic indicators Limitations: Participants from one county in Central North Carolina (mid-sized city) Sample size was highly educated (> 47.8% undergraduate degree & higher). Few Latinos included Notes: Study design is directly applicable for DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			Clinical assessment at baseline, every 6-months x 24-months	Glucose (mg/dL) = ↑ 1.89 Insulin (μU/mL) = ↓ 3.03 Overall results greater for LWL vs. UCC	
Examine the 10-year cost effectiveness of lifestyle interventions or Metformin use in DPP/ DPPOS (Herman et al., 2012)	Randomized Control Trial IV: DPP (1of 3 interventions): -Lifestyle changes include: goal-based diet, PE/PA, 16 sessions over a 24-week period -Metformin 850 mg BID -Placebo BID DV: Cost, cost effectiveness, QOL,	<i>n</i> = 3,234	The QALY measure was assessed by the health utility score Health utilities assessed annually using the self-administered quality of well-being index (QWB-SA) For the base case analysis, the researchers followed the recommendations of the panel on cost-effectiveness in health in medicine The analysis of lifestyle, metformin & placebo were based on the design, cost & clinical effectiveness of the interventions as implemented in the 3 years of the DPP & the 7 years of the DPPOS	Undiscounted per capita direct medical costs of the interventions discussed in the DPP program, were greater for lifestyle (\$4,601) than metformin (\$2,300) or placebo (\$769) The cumulative direct medical costs of care outside the DPP/DPPOS were least for lifestyle (\$24,563 lifestyle vs. \$25,616 metformin vs. \$27,468 placebo) The cumulative combined total direct medical costs were greatest for lifestyle & least for metformin (\$29,164 lifestyle vs. \$27,915 metformin vs. \$28,236 placebo)	Conclusion: Screen for glucose tolerance in the overweight & obese population Implement lifestyle interventions & metformin use as they have favorable cost-effective ratios Limitations: DPPOS was an observational FU of the DPP The costs of medical care outside the interventions appear low compared with those reported in the literature for people with DM

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				The cumulative QALY accrued over 10 years were greater for lifestyle (6.81) than metformin (6.69) or placebo (6.67)	<p>Researchers recognize in assessing the direct nonmedical costs of the interventions they overestimated diet related costs</p> <p>Notes: Relevant to DNP project</p>

APPENDIX D
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Health Care Provider Barriers

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Evaluate the relationship between attitudes towards prediabetes as a clinical construct & screening/txment behaviors for DM prevention among U.S. family physicians (Mainous et al., 2016)	Quantitative study IV: Physician attitudes DV: Prediabetes screening	1,248 family physicians US	Attitude toward prediabetes was calculated using a summated scale (5-point Likert type scale) assessing agreements with statements as a clinical construct	Physicians who have a (+) attitude toward prediabetes as a clinical construct are more likely to follow national guidelines for screening ($p < .0001$) & recommend metformin ($p < .0001$) Physicians perceived the following as barriers to treatment: -Patient economic resources -Sustaining patient motivation -Patient's ability to modify his/her lifestyle	Conclusion: Significant variation of how physicians view prediabetes as a strategy for diabetes prevention In order to improve DM prevention in FM, a multifaceted approach is needed that targets physicians' understanding & compliance with guidelines Limitations: Respondents were from all academic settings Result of this study cannot be generalized to all family physicians

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				-Time to educate patient about prediabetes	Bias among some participants based on their interest in the questions Notes: Applicable to DNP project
Conduct an overview of systematic reviews to evaluate the effectiveness of multifaceted interventions in comparison to single component interventions in changing health care professionals' behavior in clinical settings (Squires, Sullivan, Eccles, Worswick, & Grimshaw, 2014)	Systematic review IV: Multifaceted interventions DV: Changing HCP behaviors	34 reviews	Varied by study	3 reviews provided effect size/dose response statistical analyses of the effectiveness of multifaceted interventions: no statistical evidence of a relationship between the # of intervention components & the effect size 8 reviews reported direct (non statistical) comparisons of multifaceted interventions to single component interventions 23 reviews indirectly compared the effectiveness of multifaceted to single	Conclusion: No evidence that multifaceted interventions are more effective than single component interventions Limitations: Limited inclusion to reviews published in the Rx for Change database Did not search for grey literature Did not retrieve data from primary studies Notes: Findings applicable to DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
				interventions, 9 which reported a statistical analysis or reported a non-statistical direct comparison	
Explore the use of specific innovations in primary care (Goldberg, 2012)	Cross sectional research design IV: FM physicians, Primary care physicians, practice size DV: Degree of innovation in primary care practices	700 primary care practices Virginia, US	1. Team based care measured by responding to survey questions 2. EHR for internal coordination 3. EHR for external coordination 4. Patient registries 5. Clinical guidelines 6. Enhanced access to care 7. Use of patient satisfaction surveys 8. Performance measurement & monitoring	Positive link between organizational size, organizational relationships & stakeholder expectations Negative association was identified between competition & the level of the innovation No relationship degree between Medicare, managed care penetration & innovation	Conclusion: Primary care practices trying to adopt new innovations are bound by major constrains such as limited resources & influenced by patients & other stakeholders Expectations from patients & professional organizations influence the level of innovation in primary care Limitations: The study only captured information on practices at one point in time Survey instrument limited the # & types of innovation

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Evaluate custom software which is designed to simplify communications between health care provider & patient. Software is intended to change patient behavior & in the process prevent development of DM (Mann et al., 2012)	Randomized control trial IV: ADAPT tool DV: Change in physical activity, changes in HbA1c, diet	20 primary care providers 60 patients: 30 IG 30 CG Large urban academic medical center	Baseline measures: (Patient level) Patient survey based on validated survey instruments & the following domains: -demographics -medical history -health status -PA -diet -family history -prediabetes knowledge -DM risk perception (Provider level) -years in practice -attitudes/ prediabetes counseling FU: (Patient level) 3 months & 6 months (Provider level) 6 months, process outcomes Data monitoring & Quality control	Custom software is embedded in the HER The research team have conducted a series of near live usability testing simulations The system has allowed for a pre-encounter survey to explore patients' behavior change goals Patients interact with a website that collects their behavior data over time The final ADAPT system was being piloted when this study was published	Notes: Relevant to DNP project Conclusion: If successful, this customized software has the potential to be adaptable to HER& be a behavior change tool that can be utilized by HCPs Limitations: Pilot RCT, underpowered to detect anything but an extremely large change in the primary outcome: (PA) Notes: Relevant to DNP project as all documentation at present time is via EHR

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Describe the development & initial feasibility testing of the ADAPT program in order to enhance counseling about behavior change in patients with prediabetes (Lin et al., 2012)	Proof of concept pilot RCT	Convenience sample	Use of technology	At baseline the average A1c was 5.6% & at 3 months it remained at 5.6%	Conclusion: Initial findings demonstrate that the ADAPT program is feasible for helping improve PCPs counseling for behavior change in prediabetes Limitations: Convenience sample Small sample size Pilot study Notes: Relevant to DNP project as all documentation at present time is via EHR
	IV: ADAPT program DV: Behavior change	2 female PCPs 4 patients with prediabetes Study approved by IRB	Interview strategies Provider interviews Patient interviews	Patients' exercise goal to increase # of steps ranged from 500-2000 extra steps Average baseline steps per day as measured by the pedometer ↑ @ 3months Some patients responded to the tailored reminders The HCP reported the goal setting tool served as a reminder to them to counsel their prediabetes patients	

APPENDIX E
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Patient Barriers

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
Explore how prediabetic adults perceive their risk of developing DM & examine their preferences for evidence-based treatment (O'Brien et al., 2016)	Qualitative study IV: Lifestyle changes (diet, nutrition, PA) & the use of metformin DV: Prevention of DM, risk reduction	35 adult patients with prediabetes 2 large Midwest primary care practices	Semi-structured interviews	1. Multiple knowledge gaps about prediabetes & little knowledge about the illness & its management 2. Evidence about DM risk & treatment options for prediabetes is motivating to patients 3. Both intensive lifestyle changes & metformin medication are considered acceptable treatments	Conclusion: The study highlights potential opportunities to promote patient centered dialogue about prediabetes in primary care settings & may encourage action to be done by the patient Most patients consider both intensive lifestyle interventions & metformin use acceptable Limitations: Qualitative interviews provided patient perceptions but did not allow researchers to predict future behaviors or the ability to

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
					<p>generalized to broad populations</p> <p>Self-selection bias</p> <p>Study was not designed to empirically test strategies about prediabetes info.</p> <p>Notes: Relevant to DNP project</p>
<p>Examine DM illness among a sample of at risk adults according & specific characteristics that make them vulnerable to DM</p> <p>(Strauss et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Qualitative Study</p> <p>IV: Illness perceptions</p> <p>DV: HbA1c, DM related symptoms, DM knowledge</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 372</p> <p>Comprehensive care clinics New York University College of Dentistry</p>	<p>T-tests were used to determine if statistical significance was present in 8 dimensions of perception based on absence or presence of 6 at risk factors for DM</p> <p>DM illness perceptions were measured with the Brief Illness Perceptions Questionnaire (Brief IPQ-Diabetes)</p> <p>General DM Knowledge Assessment: contained 6 items R/T the effect of DM on glucose, DM diet, types of</p>	<p>Participants had a wide range of knowledge gaps & misperceptions & differences in dimensions of DM illness perceptions depending on specific DM related risk factors</p> <p>When non modifiable risk factors were present there were statistically significant differences in 2 of the illness perceptions components for the younger (18-44) & older participants (45 or older)</p>	<p>Conclusion: Due to differences in the DM related illness perceptions of adults at risk for prediabetes, it is imperative for health care providers & DM educators to personalize DM related education & management</p> <p>Limitations: Self-report nature of the data collected</p> <p>Recruitment of at risk participants in an urban oral health care</p>

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			DM, awareness of DM status, causes of DM & ↑ BG levels	(2.5 vs. 1.9 respectively; $p = 0.19$) & (4.7 vs. 3.8, respectively: $p = .030$)	location, limiting the generalizability of the findings Notes: Findings relevant to DNP project
Assess the baseline knowledge, perceptions, attitudes & behaviors of prediabetic patients in order to tailor a new technology enhanced primary care based lifestyle modification intervention (Kolb et al., 2015)	Randomized controlled pilot study IV: (ADAPT) tool DV: Baseline knowledge, perceptions, attitudes & behaviors	54 adults with prediabetes 2 Urban academic primary care practices affiliated with Mount Sinai Hospital in New York	All participants completed a 60-item multiple choice pre enrollment survey Survey assessed participants current stage of change according to the Trans-Theoretical Model of Stages of Change Symptoms of Depression & Anxiety were assessed using the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-8) & the General Anxiety Disorder (GAD-2) scale respectively Self-reported diet behavior was assessed using the short Rapid Eating Assessment for Patients (REAP-S) tool: 16 item instrument to address dietary intake & behavior	82 % female, 89% with comorbid conditions, mean BMI = 36 participants exhibited ↑ risk of DM knowledge (knowledge score = 20 on a 32-point scale) & high levels of willingness to make changes to ↓ DM risk # of daily steps was inversely correlated with perceived PA ($r = 0.35082, p < 0.0001$) Poorer scores on diet quality were inversely correlated with BMI; this (-) correlation was moderate in strength ($r = -0.042, p = 0.0017$)	Conclusion: Primary care patients are candidates for simple & efficient action planning interventions Limitations: Small sample size Single institution Urban setting, therefore generalizability is limited Participants were recruited randomly from a clinical database (selection bias) Notes: Relevant to DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			Participants were required to wear a pedometer		
Examine the association between perceived neighborhood problems & DM outcomes (Moreno et al., 2014)	Cross-sectional survey study IV: Neighborhood perceptions DV: (Primary) LDL/Cholesterol, HbA1c, blood pressure & BMI (Secondary) Participation in self-care activities	250 adults Migrant health center, rural county San Joaquin Valley, California	BMI was calculated using patient's weight/height obtained from the medical record & classified, as normal, overweight & obese AIC, LDL-c, BMI & BP values were all collected through electronic registry & medical record reviews & dichotomized Summary of DM Self Care Activities (SCDA) questionnaire was used to measure patient participation in eating a healthy diet, exercise, medication & glucose self-monitoring Presence of depressive symptoms was measured with the PHQ-2 questionnaire Self-reported health status was measured by asking	48% perceived at least 1 neighborhood problem & out of the 6 problem areas, crime was most commonly perceived as a problem among patients that perceived 1 or more neighborhood problems, mean BMI was higher ($p < 0.01$) & mean PHQ-2 scores were higher ($p < 0.001$) than those without perceived problems Mean systolic BP was 4.5 mm Hg higher ($p = 0.06$) for patients that perceived neighborhood problems compared to those without neighborhood problems	Conclusion: Perception of neighborhood problems among low income rural Latinos with DM was independently associated with a \uparrow BMI & \uparrow BP Limitations: Cross sectional design does not allow for inference of causal relationships Used self-reports which are subject to recall bias Results of this study cannot be generalized to all patients The focus of this study was on one rural agricultural region

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			participants how they would in general rate their health (excellent, very good, good, fair or poor)		Notes: Relevant to DNP project
Examine which influences reported by patients predict uptake & completion of formal lifestyle changes (Murray et al., 2012)	Systematic review IV: Patient reported factors DV: Lifestyle changes	<i>n</i> = 32 studies 5 US 7 UK 9 Australia 4 Canada 4 Rest of Europe 3 Middle East	Vary by study	374 factors extracted Factors most consistently associated with uptake of lifestyle changes: -support from family/friends -transport & related costs -beliefs about the causes of illness & lifestyle change -depression -anxiety	Conclusion: Small # of factors which are influential in completion of lifestyle behavior changes. These factors should be considered during patient consultations to promote a tailored approach about decision making Limitations: Paucity of research into long-term conditions & changing lifestyle behaviors through formal programs. Lifestyle changes in programs other than cardiac rehab was not achieved Notes: Relevant to DNP project

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
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Note. (Sorted Alphabetically): A1C = hemoglobin A1C; ADA = American Diabetes Association; ADAPT TRIAL = Avoiding Diabetes Mellitus thru Action Plan Targeting; AHEI Score = Alternative Healthy Eating Index; Alive-PD = Turnaround Health Prevent Diabetes program; ANOVA = analysis of variance; BG = blood glucose; BMI = body mass index; BP = blood pressure; BW = body weight; CA = California; CBC = community based clinic; CBS = community based system; CG = control group; CHOL = cholesterol; CHW = community health workers; CI = confidence interval; CW = community worker; DBP = diastolic blood pressure; DM = diabetes mellitus; DNP = doctorate of nursing practice; DPP = Diabetes Prevention Program; DPPOS = Diabetes Prevention Program Outcomes Study; DRC = diabetes risk calculator; DRS = diabetes risk score; DV = dependent variable; EE = exercise endurance; EG = experimental group; EHR = electronic health record; Euro QOL = Europe Quality Of Life Scale; FBG = fasting blood glucose; FG = fasting glucose; FLIP = facilitated lifestyle intervention prescription; FM = family medicine; FP = family practice; FPG = fasting plasma glucose; FPP = family practice physician; FU = follow-up; GAD-2 = Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale; GEE = General Estimating Equation Model; HAPA = health action process approach; HbA1c = hemoglobin A1c; HCP = health care provider; HDL = high density lipoprotein; HER = health electronic record; HR = heart rate; HTN = hypertension; I/IR = insulin/insulin resistance; ID = identify; IFG = impaired fasting glucose; IFPG = impaired fasting plasma glucose; IG = intervention group; ILS = intensive lifestyle; IRB = institutional review board; IV = independent variable; IVR = interactive voice response; LDL = low density lipoprotein; LWL = lifestyle weight loss; MNT = medical nutrition therapy; PA = physical activity; PCP = primary care provider; PHQ-8 = patient health questionnaire scale; Prof = professional; QALY = quality adjusted life years; QOL = quality of life; QWB-SA = Quality Of Well-Being Scale Self-Administered; R-CHO = refined carbohydrates; RCT = randomized control trial; RD = registered dietician; RDN = registered dietician nutritionist; REAP-S = Rapid Eating Assessment for Patients – Screening Tool; Rx = prescription; SBP = systolic blood pressure; SCG = standard care group; Total CHOL = total cholesterol; TRIG = triglycerides; UC = usual care; UK = United Kingdom; US = United States; UCC = usual care condition; VIT = vitamin; WC = waist circumference; WW = Weight Watchers.

APPENDIX F

PREDIABETES ALGORITHM

APPENDIX G

IRB EXEMPTION LETTER FROM ORGANIZATION

InterOffice Memorandum

Institutional Review Board
Kaiser Permanente Southern California

6/2/2017

To: Lupe Yepez-Michel, NP
Special Care
2200 E. Gonzales Road
Oxnard, CA 93036

Re: "Optimizing Prediabetes Care"

Dear Ms. Yepez-Michel,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (d) and (f). Therefore, IRB review of this project is not necessary.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Armida Ayala".

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

APPENDIX H

IRB APPROVAL LETTER/E-MAIL FROM INSTITUTION

IRB Approval of New Application HSR-17-0222 Inbox x

to me, Deanna, Elaine, Theresa

 CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Dear Lupe Yopez-Michel,

Re: **Optimizing Prediabetes Care**

The above mentioned protocol submission has been reviewed and approved. The IRB Approval notice and consent form (if applicable) will be sent via campus mail to your Faculty Advisor, Dr. Deanna Jung, in the School of Nursing.

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact our office at irb@fullerton.edu.

Ms. Theresa Tuckman
IRB Research Compliance Coordinator
Office of Research and Sponsored Projects
IRB /IACUC – **Mail Code: ASC-231**
1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831
[\(657\) 278-7640](tel:(657)278-7640)